

ABDURAHIM YUSUF-ZADE'S DIPLOMATIC ACTIVITY IN THE EMIRATE OF AFGHANISTAN

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Abstract

This article talks about the activity of the ambassador and jadid from Andijan Abdurahim Yusufzada in the Emirate of Afghanistan, his contribution to economic, social and diplomatic relations between Bukhara and Afghanistan.

Keywords: Amonullah Khan, Amir Said Olimkhan, BPSR, Mahmud Tarzi, Raskolnikov, Osmankhoja, Hashim Shayiq

On September 15, 1920, the day after the establishment of the Bukhara People's Council Republic, the new government in Bukhara proposed establishing mutual diplomatic relations in a telegram sent to the Afghan emir, Amonullah Khan.[3] The offer was accepted by Omonullah Khan. In his letter to the government of Bukhara, the Minister of Foreign Affairs of Afghanistan, Mahmud Tarzi, stated that Afghanistan never wanted Bukhara Sharif to be deprived of its prestige and independence. He also said that the new ambassador is preparing to perform his duties in the near future, and that former ambassador Abdushukurkhan will be busy protecting Afghan citizens and performing his duties until the new embassy is established.[1] With the consent of Amir Omonullah Khan, in November 1920, Abdulkhadi Khan, Chief Ghulam Siddiq Khan, Mirza Ghulam Haidar Khan, a total of 15 people, came to the Republic of Bukhara. The embassy mission has been given wide powers, and the tasks of carefully studying the situation in Bukhara have been set. The ambassador of Afghanistan in Bukhara, Abdulkhadi Khan, was one of the most famous people in Afghanistan and one of the closest officials of the emir, and he was considered the "right hand" of the minister of foreign affairs, Mahmud Tarzi.

The Chairman of the Council of BPSR and the Minister of Foreign Affairs, Fayzulla Khojaev, approves the candidate of Abdurahim Yusufzada, who is working in the position of land and water affairs supervisor at that time, who can speak several languages fluently, and who is originally from Andijan, for the task of establishing diplomatic relations with Afghanistan. In his telegram to the foreign minister of Afghanistan, Fayzullah Khojaev said that an emergency delegation led by Abdurahimkhan Yusufzada was sent to establish friendly relations between the two countries, and therefore the authority of Qori Habibullah, who was sent as a representative to Afghanistan by the former emir Said Olimkhan, was terminated, and every appeal and statement made by him said that he was indifferent." [6]

On January 19, 1921, Makhmud Tarzi sent a reply note to Faizulla Khojayev, the foreign minister of the Republic of Bukhara, through Y.Z.Surits, the ambassador of the RSFSR in Afghanistan. In it, the special letter of the Minister of Foreign Affairs of Bukhara, Fayzulla Khujaev, dated January 18, 1921, was accepted by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Afghanistan, and the news about the strengthening of ties of friendship, respect, and alliance,

and the news that the Embassy of the Government of Bukhara, headed by Mudarris Abdurrahim Yusuf, was sent to Kabul caused him to rejoice. It was noted that the government of Bukhara would approve the opening of an emergency embassy in the center of Afghanistan. [4]

On March 8, 1921, a delegation of Bukhara ambassadors solemnly entered the city of Kabul. Amir Omonullah Khan allocated a large building for them in the city center. A.Yusufzada presented a special greeting from the state of Bukhara in a meeting with the Afghan Minister of Foreign Affairs Mahmud Tarzi. On March 14, 1921, Yusufzada met face-to-face with the Amir of Afghanistan, Amonullah Khan. They talked about Bukhara and the reasons for the people's revolution. In the conversation with Yusufzada, Amonullah Khan expressed several objections to the Republic of Bukhara.

At this time, in addition to the newly established embassy of the Republic of Bukhara, the embassy of the former Emirate of Bukhara was still operating. The Afghan people knew the BPSR embassy as the "Bolshevik" embassy, and the former emir's office as the "old embassy". After it was discovered that the former Embassy of the Emirates was conducting active propaganda against the government of the BPSR, A.Yusufzada immediately wrote a note to the Minister of Foreign Affairs and achieved the termination of this embassy within three days. [8]

At the same time, by March 1921, all the territories of Eastern Bukhara were transferred from the supporters of the former emir Said Olimkhan to the government of the Soviet Union, and the emir himself was forced to go to Afghanistan with his remaining army. This situation was noticed by the People's Commissar of Foreign Affairs of the RSFSR, G.V.Chicherin, who sent a special telegram to his representative in Afghanistan, Y.V.Surits. In it, G.V.Chicherin feared that Amir Alim Khan might pass through Afghanistan to the territory of India, and Ambassador A.Yusufzada told the Bukhara embassy mission that the following was necessary: 1) to push the military detachment of the emir further inward from the border line; 2) disarming the military detachment; 3) treat the emir as an individual and prevent him from forming new military units to return to the government. Taking into account all of the above, it was noted that the Afghan emir's soldiers will be completely disarmed, 200 armed cavalry will be left as a personal guard, and Afghanistan will consider the emir only as a guest. [5]

A.Yusufzada provided valuable information about Amir Said Olimkhan during his embassy career. He stated in his embassy reports that Said Alim Khan was living in Khanabad, Afghanistan, in the same way as he used to live in Bukhara.

During his diplomatic career in Kabul, Abdurrahim Yusufzada took measures to ensure the military and political independence of the BPSR. It is envisaged that Afghanistan will be the main ally of Bukhara. With this goal in mind, in June 1921, after several months of negotiations, a Bukhara-Afghan friendship treaty was drawn up under the leadership of A. Yusufzada and Mahmud Tarzi. Even the People's Commissar of Foreign Affairs of the RSFSR, G. V. Chicherin, emphasized this in his report to the 9th Congress of Soviets. The agreement officially confirmed that both Bukhara and Afghanistan are fully independent states. The agreement was sharply criticized by the newly appointed representative of the RSFSR in Afghanistan, F. F. Raskolnikov. For example, paragraph 2 of the Afghan-Bukhara treaty stipulates that neither Afghanistan nor Bukhara will keep any foreign army in their territories. It was clear that this clause was directed against the military units of the Red Army that were in Bukhara at that time. Also, paragraph 3 of the agreement stipulates the need to return the

military units of the Red Army in Karki and Termiz, according to paragraph 5, the establishment of a joint commission from both sides to protect the important religious monuments of Muslims located in Bukhara, and according to paragraph 6, compensation will be paid to Afghan citizens who suffered from the revolution in Bukhara. The soviet government immediately took measures to prevent the signing of this agreement. The government of the RSFSR demands a revision of the Afghan-Bukhara friendship treaty and presents the Bukhara government with another treaty that takes into account the interests of the RSFSR. In this agreement, in contrast to the agreement concluded by Yusufzada, clause 2, that is, "withdrawal of foreign troops", is replaced by the clause "the two sides will not keep persons and organizations hostile to each other in their territory, and will not allow them to distribute and store weapons." In this way, the issue of the presence of the Soviet Red Army in Bukhara will be positively resolved. The clauses of compensation payment and withdrawal of military units are excluded from the text of the contract. The Soviet government immediately sent another authorized person from the Republic of Bukhara and demanded that the agreement approved by the RSFSR be signed, and A. Yusufzada was completely removed from the task of concluding the agreement.[9] Also, Afghan Foreign Minister Mahmud Tarzi met with Abdurahim Yusufzada on June 18, 1921 and stated that Soviet Russia was grossly violating the independence of the republics of Bukhara and Khiva and emphasized that this policy was directed against Muslims.[9] In August 1921, the Bukhara government, under strong political pressure from the RSFSR, was forced to sign the Afghan-Bukhara friendship treaty "recommended" by them.[10]

The Soviet government carefully monitors the actions of Osmankhoja Polathojaev, a statesman who has a great reputation in Bukhara, in Afghanistan, and F.Raskolnikov, the representative of the RSFSR in Kabul, demands from the ambassador of the BPSR, Abdurahim Yusufzade, to find out the reason why Usmanhoja Polathojaev left Bukhara. The reason why A. Yusufzoda was involved in this issue was that he and Usmonkhoja Polathojaev were colleagues and like-minded in the revolutionary movements in Bukhara.

A. Yusufzoda sends Mirzo Muhammad Sharifkhoja, the secretary of the BPSR embassy in Kabul, to Usmonkhoja Polathojaev and finds out where he lives. According to the information provided by Sharifkhoja, Usmonkhoja Polathojaev will leave Bukhara together with Ali Reza, the head of the military affairs of the USSR, but he will stay in Mazari Sharif, and Usmonkhoja Polathojaev will go to Kabul alone. He also talks to a man named Ghazi Khoja on the way. Having learned about this, A.Yusufzoda met Ghazi Khoja and recorded the details of his conversation with Usmonkhoja Polathojaev. According to him, Usmonkhoja Polathojaev, who initially joined Anvar Pasha, now has to live alone in Kabul, because his former comrades Ali Reza and Daniyor stopped supporting him. Usmonkhoja Polathojaev was being pursued by the Russians on the one hand, and by the Lakai tribe of the Hisar mountains on the other. In March 1921, Yusufzada managed to meet Usman Khoja face to face. During the conversation, Yusufzada asked, "Why did you run away here?" to his question, Usmonkhoja Polathojaev said that the Russians were robbing ordinary citizens, that they were suffering, that they were engaged in robbing the population under the pretext of fighting against "basmatchi", and there were many other similar crimes. According to A. Yusufzada's information, the Afghan government will not leave Usmankhoja alone and force him to sign various documents. After this conversation, Yusufzada sends a telegram to the government of Bukhara to defend the

honor of Osmankhoja and writes that he is guilty of only one issue, that is, of being a comrade with Anvar Pasha. [12]

No matter how much the Republic of Bukhara tried to establish independent relations in Afghanistan, these relations were controlled by both Moscow and the RSFSR embassy in Kabul. At the same time, A.Yusufzada opposed not only the British, but also the Soviet government's interference in the internal affairs of Bukhara. Therefore, he sent a letter to the ambassador of the RSFSR in Kabul, F. F. Raskolnikov, sharply condemning the policy of the Soviet government towards the independentists in Eastern Bukhara. The letter clearly states that the Russian government is also to blame for the unrest in the Republic of Bukhara, that they are grossly interfering in the internal affairs of Bukhara, and that these actions do not correspond to the cooperation agreements. [2]

In that complicated situation, Ambassador A. Yusufzada works hard to improve Afghan-Bukhara relations. However, it was not acceptable to the government of Afghanistan and the government of the RSFSR that he should serve only for the interests of the independent republic of Bukhara. As a result, on February 11 and 13, 1922, it was decided to recall A. Yusufzada to Bukhara without any warning or reason. In June 1922, Hashim Shaik arrived in Kabul as the new ambassador of Bukhara People's Soviet Republic.

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